

European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure
PLUS

Piloting of eLTER-ICOS co-operation towards the Climate-Water-GHG nexus at the pan-European scale

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Table of contents

1	Preface	4
2	Summary	4
3	Conceptual model for Research Infrastructure Co-location	4
3.1	Rationale	4
3.2	Model Components	5
3.2.1	Sites	6
3.2.2	Research Infrastructures (RIs)	6
3.2.3	Standard Observations (SO)	9
3.2.4	Long-term Legacy Observations (LLOs)	9
3.2.5	Verifiable Regional Predictions (VRPs)	10
3.2.6	Policy Relevant Indicators (PRIs)	10
3.2.7	Other Aspects of RI Co-location	11
4	Co-location with other networks and Research Infrastructures	11
4.1	eLTER, ICOS and ENVRI	11
4.2	Cooperation with ICOS	13
4.3	A taxonomy for networks and Research Infrastructures	14
4.3.1	Sub-national programmes and infrastructures	14
4.3.2	National Infrastructures	15
4.3.3	International networks and Infrastructures	15
4.3.4	RI Level of maturity	16
4.4	Collaboration and Co-location	17
5	Virtual Co-location	17
5.1	Conceptual Approach	17
5.2	Lessons from ICOS	19
5.3	Example Workflow	19
6	Acknowledgements	20
7	References	21
8	Glossary	26

1 Preface

The aim of this task was to explore the potential benefits of the eLTER and ICOS Research Infrastructures (RIs) co-location for generating and communicating new insights into the pan European water-climate-GHG nexus. This new knowledge is needed to better constrain estimates of the pan-European GHG emission and carbon footprint and to help build the evidence base needed for decisions related to national and European climate mitigation targets. The task has three components. First, we developed a conceptual model of RI co-location (Section 4). Second, we explored the potential for co-location and collaboration with ICOS and other entities (Section 5). Finally, we motivate and present a workflow for virtual co-location (Section 6).

2 Summary

Collaboration is a cornerstone of the eLTER vision. Co-location, or the participation of two or more environmental research networks and infrastructures (ERNIs) at the same location, is a form of collaboration that can increase the value of site-based observations for both the scientific community and decision makers. While this task has focused primarily on the benefits and challenges of co-location with the Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS), co-location with other relevant ERNIs is also discussed.

There are both physical and virtual aspects to co-location. Physical co-location involves multiple RIs collecting data and sharing resources at the same sites. Virtual co-location occurs when these data are accessible from the same data portal. The value of physical co-location where multiple ERNIs make observations at the same physical locations is clear but the challenges of assembling and synthesizing data from multiple ERNIs highlights the need for virtual co-location. The vision for virtual co-location presented here consists of applying workflows needed to make datasets from multiple ERNIs discoverable through the same portal. These workflows are complementary to the tasks being pursued in eLTER PLUS Work Packages 10 and 11.

Tangible outputs of the task include conference presentations at EGU in 2022 (Futter et al. 2021) and 2024 as well as the 2022 ICOS Science Conference, conference session organization for the 2024 EGU and ICOS Science Conferences and a peer reviewed paper (Futter et al. 2023).

Recommendations:

- Continue to promote and communicate the benefits of physical co-location with ICOS and other ERNIs to funders, site managers, researchers and the ENVRI community (ENVRI; cluster for Environmental RIs in the EU)
- Evaluate and implement best practices developed by US (GLEON, NEON), European (ICOS) and other ERNIs to guide the eLTER RI roadmap
- Promote, communicate and implement distributed (site level) workflows and protocols needed to make data sets machine discoverable, thereby promoting virtual co-location

3 Conceptual model for Research Infrastructure Co-location

3.1 Rationale

A high-level conceptual model can help to understand benefits and potential drawbacks of Research Infrastructure (RI) physical co-location. By participating in one or more RIs, individual sites gain access

to a suite of services including data, access, computational and support services. Data services conforming to FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016) as well as standardised and quality controlled data products are provided through specific RI portals and ultimately through the European Open Science Cloud. Access services can be physical, remote and virtual for in-situ sampling and measurement campaigns as well as for off-site use of experimental facilities and scientific resources. Computational services can include virtual research environments, data analysis systems, visualization tools and modelling platforms. Support services include scientific workshop organization, education and training.

3.2 Model Components

A conceptual model for RI co-location should include the following components: in-situ observing sites, research infrastructures, standardised observing protocols, long-term legacy observations, verifiable regional predictions and policy relevant indicators (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Components of a conceptual model for research infrastructure (RI) co-location from Futter et al. (2023). The model includes sites (sites A–I, represented as circles), long-term legacy observations (LLOs; stars), research infrastructures (RIs, rectangles), verifiable regional predictions (VRPs; rectangles with rounded corners), standard observations (SOs; pentagonal arrowheads) and policy relevant indicators (PRIs; cloud). Arrows connecting sites to a SO indicate that the site makes observations using a standardised protocol suitable for generation of a VRP. Protocols for each SO are owned by an RI. The ability of a site to contribute to PRIs is indicated by the darkness of the vertical arrows connecting sites and PRIs with darker arrows indicating stronger contributions (e.g., sites E, F and G make a stronger contribution than sites C and D). There are three RIs in the figure (RI(1)–RI(3)). RI(1) makes observations using three SO protocols, RI(2) has five and RI(3) has four. Only observations made using SO protocols can contribute to the development of VRPs. Site A only collects LLOs. Thus, it has the least ability to support PRIs and is not able to contribute to the generation of VRPs. Sites C and D participate in a single RI (RI(1)) and make observations using SO

protocols developed by that RI. Site B can make a more effective contribution to PRIs as it has both LLOs and participates in an RI where it makes observations using SO protocols. As sites H and I co-locate RI(2) and RI(3), they can contribute to the development of VRPs. Furthermore, they have a greater ability to contribute to PRI development than sites that do not have co-located RIs. Sites E, F and G can make the strongest contribution to PRI development as they make observations using SO protocols for all three RIs.

3.2.1 Sites

A site¹ is a definable geographical area where in-situ observations are made of the natural and/or human environment that support research and societal decision-making. Sites typically employ one or more people to support operations, make in-situ observations and manage data. Sites are typically managed by one or more public sector entities (e.g., university, government agency, research institute, etc.). When operational responsibilities are shared between organisations, different entities are typically responsible for different types of observations, i.e., one would be responsible for water observations, another for gas concentration measurements and a third for biodiversity. Sites are either owned by the managing entity or secured under long-term agreement. Site operations are usually funded through a range of short- or long-term financial instruments including competitive grants, service contracts, internal institute resources and various national and European programmes.

Sites do not necessarily have sharp geographical boundaries but can be geo-located using a centroid, representative coordinates or bounding polygons. Usually, sites have one or more observing locations (e.g., plots, weirs, flux towers, etc.) (Wohner et al, 2022). Observations can be made using instruments (e.g., water level recorders, spectrophotometers), surveys (e.g., vegetation, birds, etc.), collection and analysis of material from the site (e.g., sampling biota, water or soil), document analysis (e.g. land tenure records) or personal contacts with people living and working at or near to the site (e.g., interviews, surveys).

Depending on available resources and awareness levels, site data are managed in a more or less structured manner, ranging from effectively undocumented spreadsheets on individual researcher's computers through robust, centralised IT systems with all necessary metadata (e.g., the ICOS Carbon Portal, Heiskanen et al. 2022). Data management is easier to professionalise when observing and reporting methods are harmonised, as is the case at sites participating in RIs. Such sites are typically more committed to FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016) and third party data access. Criteria for third party access and use of data can range from none through complicated and restrictive licenses. Increasing pressure from the scientific community, funding bodies and the European Commission to ensure data are compliant with FAIR principles is gradually improving data access, as is RI membership and the associated demands for standardised data management. Online catalogues (e.g. DEIMS; Wohner et al. 2019) are important sources of site metadata and there is increasing recognition of the need to develop the necessary IT infrastructure for sharing data within and between RIs (Huber et al. 2021). Crediting data authors using internationally recognised and persistent identifiers can also improve data access (Rennie et al. 2021).

3.2.2 Research Infrastructures (RIs)

Research Infrastructures (RIs) are “umbrella” organisations that coordinate observations made at multiple sites. An individual site can participate in zero or more RIs. As RIs promote the use of standardised measurement and reporting protocols as well as centralised data services, they can offer benefits to a site through both physical and virtual co-location.

¹ <https://elter-ri.eu/lter-facilites>

Environmental RIs have existed in Europe for more than one hundred years. The RI landscape includes first, second and third generation infrastructures making observations that can contribute to a holistic understanding of the biophysical environment (Table 1). National Forest Inventories (NFIs), some of which have been in continuous operation for more than a century (McRoberts et al. 2010), are probably the most relevant first generation RI for eLTER co-location. Ideally, eLTER (and other RIs) could promote the establishment of new sites where there are existing national forest monitoring plots. The long-term measurements made at national inventory sites can give a valuable temporal perspective on the shorter time series available from, e.g., ICOS. However, it is not always straightforward to compare mensuration data collected by national programmes to modern measurements based on Standard Observing Protocols (Giuntoli et al. 2020). The main constraint with the use of NFI observations in that data are harmonised at a national level, which makes any sort of pan-European assessment extremely challenging.

Second generation RIs that are relevant candidates for eLTER co-location include networks established under the Convention on Long Range Transport of Air Pollution (CLRTAP; Wettestad 1997). Both the UNECE ICP Integrated Monitoring (IM; Vuorenmaa et al. 2017) and the ICP Forests Level II intensive monitoring programmes (Ferretti 2021) are candidates for co-location. The ICP programmes collect policy-relevant environmental data on ecosystem effects by air pollution at sites across Europe using Standard Observations (SOs) (Ferretti and Fischer 2013). In some cases, sites participating in these RIs have been making observations for almost 50 years. These long-term, standardised observations have contributed to the evidence base for emissions reduction agreements to mitigate acidification (Wettestad 1997; Dirnböck et al. 2019; Grennfelt et al. 2020) and are part of the ongoing evidence base for assessing deposition effects on the terrestrial environment related to, e.g., eutrophication (Dirnböck et al. 2018) or heavy metals (Napa et al. 2015). Standardised observations made at ICP Forests sites have also been used for assessment of forest health. For example, Penuelas et al. (2020) used data from the programme to highlight the widespread decline in foliar nutrient status of European forests and to raise a warning flag about possible loss of resilience in terrestrial carbon sequestration that would increase the uncertainty of carbon budget estimates and resulting climate change mitigation policies.

The value of first and second generation RIs should not be underestimated as they have the longest observation time series, often dating back to the first half of the twentieth century. However, these RIs are not used to the fullest possible extent because their data holdings can be difficult to access. Metadata for first generation RIs can be available only in national languages and some first generation RI data holdings are not digitized. Some of the difficulties in accessing data from first generation RIs is a legacy of their original purpose. First generation RIs originally supported national government oversight of natural resources, and second generation RIs are closely linked to CLRTAP reporting requirements. While some data produced by these RIs are open or available (e.g., by request), the historical focus of first and second generation RIs on generating data for internal use has meant that they did not prioritise the application of FAIR or other third party access principles. Today, there are encouraging moves towards greater transparency and open data access, especially amongst second generation RIs focused on evaluation of the effectiveness of international conventions and protocols.

Table 1: Selected properties of first, second and third generation European environmental research infrastructures (RIs). Extensive RIs typically make a limited number of observations at a large number of sites while intensive RIs make a large number of observations at a small number of sites.

	First Generation	Second Generation	Third Generation
Examples	National forest inventories (NFIs)	UNECE ICP Integrated Monitoring and ICP Forests	ACTRIS, ICOS, eLTER
Compliance with FAIR Principles	Low to moderate	Moderate (but increasing)	High
Extensive / Intensive	Extensive	Intensive and Extensive	Intensive
Standard Observation Protocols	Yes (national level)	Yes (international level)	Yes (international)
Cross-RI Compatibility	Low	Low to moderate	Moderate to High
Scale	National	International, Continental	Continental
Approach	Repeated inventories	Monitoring	Research, studying processes and functioning
Scope	Representative at the national scale	bottom up based on national networks	networks of networks; attempts to be spatially representative
Focus	single disciplines	multidisciplinary	Inter-, trans- or cross-disciplinary
Potential for Physical Co-location	Moderate	Low to Moderate	Moderate to High
Potential for Virtual Co-location	High	High	High

The US LTER infrastructure was one of the first third generation RIs (Keller et al. 2008). In many ways, it provided a blueprint and inspiration for subsequent RIs including TERENO (Zacharias et al. 2011), NEON (Keller et al. 2008) and the ILTER network of networks (Mirtl et al., 2018). The success of these RIs was in large part due to secure and sustained funding needed to support high quality observations, long-term data collection and information management.

Third generation RIs are characterised by significant investments in IT infrastructure, documented QA/QC protocols, a commitment to the use of SO protocols and timely and openly available data. Because of these characteristics, ICOS (Heiskanen et al. 2022) and other third generation RIs can deliver the Verifiable Regional Predictions (VRPs, described below) needed for high-impact, policy-relevant science (e.g., Migliavacca et al. 2021).

As well as the knowledge gained through observations made by individual RIs, there are significant possibilities to combine observations from multiple generations of RIs to give new insights into the policy-relevant environmental processes, e.g., terrestrial carbon cycling. One such example is given in Cabon et al. (2022). They combined first generation long-term growth measurements based on tree rings with third generation eddy covariance measurements to better constrain estimates of terrestrial carbon sequestration. These advances based on observations from multiple co-located RIs are laying the groundwork for the next generation of syntheses that connect site biogeochemistry to biodiversity and socio-ecology.

3.2.3 Standard Observations (SO)

Standard Observation (SOs) and the protocols for their collection are central to the eLTER vision. SO protocols are publicly accessible descriptions of reproducible and affordable mechanisms for characterizing and reporting environmental system states or processes. Each SO protocol is owned and maintained by an RI (e.g., ICOS protocols for flux measurement, ICP Forests protocols for vegetation monitoring) or third party (e.g., World Meteorological Organization protocols for precipitation monitoring). A SO protocol must be sufficiently well documented to allow cross-site implementation, integration and comparison. For example, observations made using the ICP Forests² and ICOS (Gielen et al. 2018) vegetation monitoring protocols can be compared with each other. One main benefit of using SOs is that they allow sites to collect observations in a consistent and harmonised manner. Consistent and harmonised observing protocols and standardised QA/QC procedures greatly simplify the synthesis of data from multiple sites and the production of Verifiable Regional Predictions (VRPs, see below). The eLTER RI is developing its SO protocols in the eLTER PLUS project within work package tasks 3.1 and 3.3.

3.2.4 Long-term Legacy Observations (LLOs)

Many sites have long time series of environmental observations, or Long-term Legacy Observations (LLOs). These include so-called “long tail” data (Heidorn 2008) that are typically collected as part of PI-led research projects. Considerable efforts within eLTER PLUS are dedicated to mobilizing LLOs from sites and platforms (particularly Tasks 4.1 and 4.5). Such efforts are needed to maximize the value of LLOs by increasing their compliance with FAIR principles. While collection protocols for LLOs are internally consistent, they may be poorly documented. In many cases, these data are not stored using modern data management practices but may be hidden away in desk drawers, filing systems and individual’s hard drives.

Protocols for LLOs are typically owned at the site level (e.g., each site or PI will have their own way of observing, QA/QC routines and data storage protocols). Metadata characterizing LLO protocols may be more or less readily available, potentially hindering implementation across sites as well as making it difficult for an individual site to share data or to make cross-site comparisons. One strength of many LLO series is continuity of personnel and internally consistent measurement protocols. This level of standardization can greatly simplify detection and attribution of signals in individual observation series. However, the main perceived drawback of LLOs is that they are difficult to compare across sites.

The insights about long-term environmental change that can be extracted from analysis of LLOs are an important part of the evidence base for Policy Relevant Indicators (PRIs; described below). However, conclusions derived from LLOs lack explicit regional context. National funders, site managers and RIs should prioritise efforts to develop inter-calibration tools for LLOs from observing sites across Europe in a seamless and harmonised manner as robust methods for translation across observing protocols are vital for informed environmental policy. To give one example of this process, the EU Water Framework Directive has a goal of achieving good ecological status in surface waters across Europe. Status assessments are based on both standardised observations and LLOs that can differ between countries. Because different countries had invested heavily in different observing strategies, there was no realistic possibility of new, pan-European SOs. This institutional bottleneck led to significant investment of scientific effort to inter-calibrate the different LLOs used across Europe for water quality monitoring (Poikane et al. 2015).

²<http://icp-forests.net/page/icp-forests-manual>

3.2.5 Verifiable Regional Predictions (VRPs)

Verifiable Regional Predictions (VRPs) are one of the most important computational services currently provided by eLTER and other RIs as they contribute to the evidence base for policies to address current and future environmental challenges. While VRPs can be created from LLOs, the process is greatly simplified when they can be based SOs made at sites participating in a RI. A key feature of VRPs is that they leverage site-based, geographically discontinuous point measurements to produce indicators (e.g., Critical Loads) that have seamless spatial and temporal coverage. The site and European-scale modelling done in the eLTER PLUS tasks 8.3 and 9.3 are good examples of this process. Inputs to VRPs may include modelling (e.g., Xu et al. 2021) and remote sensing (e.g., Ceccherini et al. 2020) but must be “ground truthed” by in-situ measurements (e.g., Pongratz et al. 2021). Ground truthing against measurements made using SOs is easier than ground truthing against LLOs as there is no need for inter-series calibration when using the former type of observation.

The spatial extent and amount of uncertainty in VRPs depends in part on the density and representativeness of sites contributing providing observations. The spatial distributions of predictions and their associated uncertainty in VRPs derived from observations at existing sites is a useful way to highlight the need for new observing sites (e.g., Wohner et al. 2021) or co-location of additional RIs at existing observing sites.

3.2.6 Policy Relevant Indicators (PRIs)

Policy Relevant Indicators (PRIs) – new, actionable insight into system behaviour – can be derived from single site LLOs or VRPs created from multi-site observations collected using SO protocols. The main difference between a VRP and a PRI is that the latter reports a parameter that can be influenced by societal action. For example, a VRP might report drought frequency while a PRI might report the extent of agricultural water conservation measures. A PRI is not the same as a policy action. PRIs provide the evidence base that decision makers can use in policy formulation as a precursor to action. The research community develops PRIs but policy decisions are ultimately made by elected decision makers and civil society.

Connections between VRPs and PRIs must be strengthened if the site-based research community is to respond and contribute to implementing the European Green Deal (EC 2019) and other societal challenges. Facilitating societal change based on the new knowledge gained from VRPs will require an appropriate and implementable communication strategy. The Green Deal identifies a number of possibilities including simple “traffic light” approaches where indicators are colour coded red, yellow or green depending on severity of potential impacts (Futter et al. 2016). Another approach would be to use the strategy exemplified by Högbom et al. (2021) where scientific synthesis supported targeted communication with EU decision makers. Tasks 8.5 and 9.5 in the eLTER PLUS project address these issues.

Both spatially extensive multi-site RI-based (i.e., VRPs) and single-site long-term (i.e. LLO) indicators are needed to support the policy process. LLOs can be used to identify background or reference conditions, as well as being an indicator of progress towards environmental goals (e.g., detecting trends). National decision makers, RIs and the site-based Earth observation community must all collaborate to ensure that the wealth of existing observations that exist in site data archives are incorporated into the provision of actionable PRIs.

3.2.7 Other Aspects of RI Co-location

While RI co-location has multiple benefits, there can be drawbacks. RI membership can be seen as an unnecessary expense by both site managers and national funding agencies. Sites may also struggle to implement SOs and may be reluctant to abandon LLO protocols. Nationally, funding agencies may feel pressured to abandon sites that do not participate in RIs. Also, the push towards FAIR and open data may not always be supported by data provider. Recognising the perceived drawbacks of RI co-location and addressing them in an open and constructive manner will contribute to stronger European science that is better able to address future environmental challenges.

Greater scientific and societal value to co-location could be achieved by “nesting” across scales. The spatially extensive, long-term plot level observations made by NFIs and other first generation RIs tend to be representative at the national level but can be challenging to use for creating pan-European PRIs. Second generation RIs such as ICP Forests and ICP IM have fewer sites but use both internationally harmonised methods (i.e., SOs) and national (LLO) methods; so national results can be calibrated with harmonised methods at the European scale. Third generation RIs offer the potential for intensive observation campaigns which can help to identify the mechanisms underlying national and regional trends reported by first and second generation RIs.

Physical co-location (site interoperability), where two or more RIs make observations at the same or nearby geographical coordinates, is a necessary condition for interoperability. However, the importance of virtual co-location (data interoperability; Wohner et al. 2020; Huber et al. 2021), should not be neglected. Standardised QA/QC protocols and a commitment to FAIR data principles greatly increase the value of multi-site observations to scientists and other end-users.

4 Co-location with other networks and Research Infrastructures

Collaboration with other RIs and networks is at the core of the eLTER mission and strategic goals. The eLTER mission statement states that “we will synergistically collaborate with diverse ecosystem environmental research infrastructures and networks across Europe and the world”. These sentiments are echoed in the fourth strategic goal which says we will “strive to establish productive and synergistic relations with related RIs across Europe and globally”.

Collaboration can occur through both formal and informal channels. One noteworthy example of the former is the recently established agreement between the UN Air Convention Working Group on Effects and eLTER. This agreement makes official the many informal collaborations that have occurred in the past and are ongoing but concrete steps towards a closer co-operation are also only just starting.

4.1 eLTER, ICOS and ENVRI

Much of the effort expended in this task and elsewhere in the project has been devoted to building better ties with ICOS. While building and maintaining these ties are important activities, the eLTER RI should not focus solely on co-location and collaboration with ICOS. There is a lot we can still learn from ICOS, and there are clear benefits for closer collaboration. With respect to co-location, ICOS are the “gold standard” for carbon flux measurements and are a key part of European efforts to quantify the carbon cycle. With respect to promoting a culture of policy-relevant science, the 2022 ICOS Science Conference in Utrecht was a masterclass in how to organize a successful scientific meeting. The upcoming 2024 ICOS Science Conference where we are co-organizing a session on the benefits of RI co-location will likely provide additional insight into the ways in which an RI can promote scientific

best practices. Specifically, the structure and organization of the ICOS Science Conferences could be a good model for the upcoming eLTER Science Conference in 2025.

On a more tangible level, the technical competence behind the recommendations for virtual co-location (Section 6) comes from informal collaboration with the ICOS Carbon Portal (Heiskanen et al. 2022), via the Swedish Infrastructure for Ecosystem Science (SITES³). Having access to workflows that will make datasets machine discoverable is integral to successful virtual co-location. It has been possible to include background information about the workflows in this deliverable because there are well functioning peer-to-peer connections between people in the ICOS Carbon Portal and SITES.

While there are multiple benefits to closer collaboration with ICOS, there are also some potential down sides. Considerable effort has been invested by both RIs in building up collaboration but the outcomes have not been as successful as might be expected given the efforts invested. Despite the significant efforts by both ICOS and eLTER, we still have room to improve formal, working collaboration. Focusing exclusively on collaboration with ICOS could detract from efforts to ensure that eLTER remains on the RI roadmap. If we focus too much on interactions with ICOS, there is a risk that the eLTER RI may be perceived as an initiative developed primarily to provide supporting and ancillary data for ICOS. The ICOS RI recognizes the need for ancillary observations to support their gas flux measurements (e.g., Jiménez et al. 2018), and a number of these observations can be collected using the eLTER Standardized Observations methodologies. This has already a misunderstanding that eLTER should exist solely to provide supporting data to ICOS.

Some guidance about the importance of co-location and collaboration can be extracted from the eLTER mission statement, part of which states: “As a fundamental component of eLTER’s identity, we will synergistically collaborate with diverse ecosystem/environmental research infrastructures and networks across Europe and the world.” For locations in Europe, further discussion is warranted around what is meant by “collaboration”. Does it mean some form of co-location where sites participating in other RIs are also eLTER sites? If it does, one question that comes immediately to mind is that of financing. Specifically, how can national (and potentially European) level funders be convinced of the need for additional investments to support the participation of additional sites in eLTER? “Synergistic collaboration” could be interpreted as information sharing and technology transfer through both formal and informal channels. Such actions would not necessarily be dependent on additional investment but could build on existing (and planned) competences within the eLTER RI. For example, it would be feasible to make greater efforts to include non-eLTER sites in DEIMS (ideally using protocols that do not place any additional demands on the people currently supporting DEIMS). The eLTER RI could also support information sharing (e.g., training about eLTER Standardized Observations) and technology transfer (e.g., workflows developed as part of the central services could be shared with outside partners or made open source).

The eLTER mission statement states that we will work with both “research infrastructures and networks”. Membership in ENVRI may not be the only defining criteria for a European RI, but it seems to be a reasonable starting point. Working with networks and RIs implies a number of things. First of all, it seems to imply that eLTER is not going to work with single, unaffiliated sites (i.e., sites not participating in any network or RI). It is not clear how many unaffiliated sites actually exist as there are so many more or less formal networks in Europe and it seems more likely than not that almost every site will belong to at least one network or RI. Second, as the statement includes both RIs and networks, eLTER should be committed to making connections in Europe beyond the ENVRI community⁴.

³ <https://www.fieldsites.se/>

⁴ <https://envri.eu/research-infrastructures/>.

4.2 Cooperation with ICOS

There are significant, mutually beneficial possibilities for closer cooperation between ICOS and eLTER. The ICOS ERIC aims at understanding the carbon and greenhouse gas budgets of terrestrial ecosystems and oceans and resulting atmospheric concentrations and transport processes. ICOS Ecosystem sites generate harmonized and standardized measurements on carbon and GHG budgets, building on more than 70 flux towers in 12 European countries, six of which are also signatories of the eLTER Expression of Support. The ICOS ecosystem community has developed detailed, standardized measurement protocols for many parameters and a process of site labelling that is complementary to the approach used in DEIMS.

While ICOS focuses primarily on atmospheric carbon and GHG flux measurements, their instruments, methods, data and workflows clearly complement the eLTER whole systems approach. The concept of the eLTER RI is very similar to the ENVRIplus RI co-location and inter-operational approach at Class 1 sites. This similarity has led to confusion and a misunderstanding that the eLTER RI aims to cover the whole spectrum of ecosystem-related observations. The eLTER Whole Systems conceptual model combines Press Pulse Dynamics and macrosystems ecology (Mirtl et al 2021). It aims to support a comprehensive understanding of ecosystems that includes observations of the carbon cycle, impacts of climate change on ecosystem functioning as well as terrestrial ecosystem GHG emissions (i.e., the core scientific tasks of the ICOS Ecosystem). This conceptual overlap is unavoidable but solvable on a practical level by cross-RI cooperation. Additional observations supported by co-location of eLTER and ICOS on, e.g., the nitrogen cycle, biodiversity or pollutants will be scientifically extremely valuable for the interpretation of core ICOS parameters while ICOS carbon and GHG flux measurements will support and augment observations made by eLTER. Furthermore, the eLTER RI includes regional multi- and transdisciplinary case study areas (eLTSER Platforms), comprising multiple spatially nested smaller scale elements for socio-ecological research that can support and complement ICOS activities.

Co-location of eLTER and ICOS across Europe could provide a broad range of long-term observations on terrestrial ecosystems in the following fields:

- 1.) **Promoting Cooperative Class 1 Sites in the National Networks of ICOS and eLTER:** This will bring clear and significant additional scientific value in the form of comprehensive and systematic observations, common data evaluation and modelling approaches, as well as a possibility to reduce construction and operational costs.
- 2.) **Construction and further development of e-infrastructures, data services and data integration platforms.** The ICOS RI has taken a leading role in clustering these efforts for environmental research infrastructures in ENVRIplus. This is an excellent framework for deepening data interoperability. The goal here is to overcome fragmentation by developing and promoting cross-RI services as developed and suggested by ENVRIplus.
- 3.) **Conceptual and technical developments:** Theoretical approaches as well as measurement techniques in ICOS and eLTER share common roots so synergies can be expected from cooperation in these fields. As an example, reactive nitrogen flux measurements with eddy covariance technology (Ferrara et al. 2012, Brümmer et al. 2013) could be an excellent field of cooperation and further development of Cooperative Class 1 Sites.

The successful adoption of a Letter of Collaboration between eLTER and the ICOS ERIC was an important milestone in formalizing collaboration between the two RIs. Integration of scientific user communities across the RIs was strengthened through a session on eLTER & ICOS co-located sites and collaboration benefits at the ICOS scientific conference in autumn 2022 (close collaboration with WP 8 & 9).

At an operational level, ICOS and eLTER are working on a pilot designed to strengthen and highlight the benefits of co-location and closer collaboration. The pilot will strengthen the case for RI co-location through, e.g., exploring possibilities for clear and mutually beneficial division of tasks and complementary development of site networks across the current geopolitical coverage of each partner.

As well as benefits to co-location and closer collaboration between RIs, there are some perceived disadvantages that must be addressed. One key point to address is related to insufficient coverage across Europe for both ICOS and eLTER with ongoing competition on membership (on the European level) and resources (on the national level). These challenges could be addressed by a novel generation of smart agreements towards European RI integration: The vision could have an “ICOS module” as part of eLTER RI Whole System Approach is compliant and taken care of by ICOS, either as a formal ICOS site or via association with ICOS. Mutually, focal components of eLTER (components of complementary biogeochemical cycles, less intensive approaches for assessing carbon budgets at larger scales or Regular Sites, biodiversity, socio-ecology) covered at ICOS sites could be formal or associated eLTER sites.

There are many synergies that can be achieved through closer collaboration between ICOS and eLTER related to scientific breakthroughs, methodological developments and technical core competences of both RIs that can be achieved by working together. The ICOS Ecosystem Thematic Centre has a world-leading position in the processing and quality assurance and control of eddy covariance-based flux measurements. The eLTER RI holds the same position in integrating nitrogen cycle and biodiversity observations, research on other pollutants/drivers and on socio-ecological interactions. To overcome competition and find parallel competences, a cross-Research-Infrastructure system of services is needed. Such an initiative would unlock enormous resources and drastically improve the science and societal relevance of both RIs if mutual services could be realized.

4.3 A taxonomy for networks and Research Infrastructures

The eLTER RI is committed to a broad spectrum of collaboration within and outside Europe. The phrase in the mission statement that identifies “diverse ecosystem/environmental research infrastructures and networks across Europe and the world”, suggests that eLTER will collaborate with ERNIs working at multiple spatial scales and multiple levels or, e.g., implementation of FAIR principles. The following section outlines a taxonomy for ERNIs based on four spatial scales (sub-national, national, European and global) and across the three generations of RIs as described by Futter et al. (2023).

4.3.1 Sub-national programmes and infrastructures

Formal collaboration with sub-national ERNIs will probably not bring significant benefit to the eLTER RI but they should be evaluated on a case-by-case basis to identify approaches, tools or workflows that could be beneficial to eLTER. For the purposes of the present discussion, a sub-national ERNI has the following characteristics: it is typically led by a single PI, it makes routine measurements at two or more locations and is dependent on soft money for its continued existence. These networks can play important scientific (e.g., Deutscher and Kupec 2014) and policy (e.g., Geranmayeh et al. 2018) roles but it is hard to see how they could fit into an eLTER roadmap. As sub-national ERNIs are not typically funded by national agencies, there is limited opportunity to formally involve them in the eLTER RI roadmap. While formal collaboration with sub-national entities is not likely, “synergistic collaboration” as presented earlier in this chapter could be mutually beneficial. Making site information available in DEIMS, promoting workflows for virtual co-location by making datasets

machine discoverable (Section 6) and sharing the eLTER Standardized Observation protocols could be mutually beneficial. In most cases, sub-national networks are likely to be out of scope as candidates for formal collaboration. One notable exception would be when sites that participate solely in sub-national networks can help with some of the gap filling, upscaling and extrapolation that is currently being scoped as part of Task 9.5. Any sort of synergistic collaboration that allowed these sites to, e.g., adopt SO protocols or inter-calibrate LLOs would facilitate their incorporation into workflows for generating VRPs and PRIs.

4.3.2 National Infrastructures

Successful collaboration with selected national-level infrastructures is a necessary part of eLTER RI roadmap as the funders of these infrastructures are the same entities that will eventually fund the RI. However, developing a comprehensive taxonomy of national-level entities is not straightforward. There are a number of axes of variability related to: (i) site membership in eLTER, (ii) national network membership in a larger “umbrella” network, (iii) institutional position between a network and an infrastructure and (iv) the importance of the national level funder to a successful eLTER RI. At one extreme, there are long term monitoring networks funded by national entities (e.g., agriculture ministries, forest agencies, etc.) that have not previously expressed an interest in eLTER. These networks do not currently participate in eLTER and most likely will not, despite the potential benefits to both parties, they are not part of a larger umbrella network and support from their funder is not crucial to the success of the eLTER RI process (e.g., the Swedish agricultural catchments monitoring programme, Ezzati et al. 2023). There might be some value to adding these sites to eLTER as part of a gap filling exercise but it is not likely to be straightforward considering different funding sources, different institutional cultures, etc. However, including these sites in DEIMS would be mutually beneficial. It would increase the visibility of their parent network as well as highlighting the role DEIMS can play within the eLTER RI process as a provider of environmental information.

The 26 national LTER networks (e.g., LTER Sweden⁵) are important ERNIs for co-location. These networks are members of LTER Europe, and there are significant overlaps in sites and personnel between these networks and the eLTER RI. Approximately 250 of the 450 or so national LTER sites will be in the eLTER RI and may be supported by the same constellation of funding agencies as will support the eLTER RI. One issue that needs to be better communicated to the national LTER networks is that the eLTER RI has a centralised, institutional existence that is separate from the individual sites in the network. This is clearly outlined in the draft governance plan of the eLTER RI, which is discussed in the Interim Council.

Nationally funded infrastructures having one or more sites currently participating in eLTER and other RIs such as SITES⁶, Tereno (Zacharias et al. 2011) and SMEAR (Hari et al. 2013) are representative of national ERNIs that should be candidates for co-location and collaboration. These national infrastructures provide examples of best practices that should be more closely integrated into eLTER RI planning (e.g., workflows to make datasets machine discoverable could be incorporated as part of the eLTER central IT strategy). The Finnish SMEAR programme is especially interesting for several reasons. First, it is an example of successful RI co-location (eLTER, AnaEE, ACTRIS and ICOS) across forest, urban and agricultural land cover types. Second, it presents a model that has been successfully exported to another European Member State (Estonia; Noe et al., 2015).

4.3.3 International networks and Infrastructures

⁵ <https://www.slu.se/en/departments/aquatic-sciences-assessment/environment/lter-sweden/>

⁶ <https://www.fieldsites.se/>

International networks and research infrastructures at the European and global scale are important collaboration partners. Clearly, LTER Europe is an important collaborator. Of the 27 RIs participating in ENVRI⁷, ACTRIS, AnaEE, INTERACT, ICOS, DANUBIUS, and others have in-situ facilities and shared interests to co-locate them with the eLTER RI.

At the European and larger scale, eLTER should be working more closely with the UNECE Air Convention supported EMEP and Working Group on Effects (WGE) networks. There are obvious synergies with ICP Forests (Ferretti 2021), ICP Integrated Monitoring (ICP IM, Vuorenmaa et al. 2017), and potentially with ICP Waters (Kvaeven et al. 2001). Both ICP Forests and ICP IM are site based infrastructures that have a similar approach to terrestrial eLTER sites and ICP Waters to aquatic eLTER sites. There is co-location of ICP and eLTER at multiple sites and some of the standard protocols developed in the ICPs have been taken up as eLTER Standardized Observations methodologies. At a more formal level, a signed “letter of collaboration” between the WGE (the head organization of all ICPs) and eLTER is an encouraging sign.

The Critical Zone Observatories (CZO; Arora et al. 2023), which are distributed globally, share similar goals and philosophies to eLTER. The CZO network and eLTER share sites personnel, notably Koliaris (Lilli et al. 2020) and there is a successful exchange of ideas between the two networks.

Outside of Europe, there are Australian (TERN; Cleverly et al. 2019) and US infrastructures that are either role models or candidates for collaboration. NEON, the National Ecological Observatory Network, is a top-down initiative that includes 47 terrestrial and 34 aquatic sites in the US where standardized measurements are collected (Jones et al, 2021). NEON started delivering data in 2015 and the organization is quite open about successes and challenges (e.g. Nagy et al 2021). As eLTER seeks to emulate the top down approach used by NEON, it would be useful to seek closer ties with them to learn what does and does not work for a centralized RI based on standardized observations. LTER, the US Long Term Ecological Research Program is a more site-based initiative. It currently includes 28 sites and the direction of research is set primarily by the site PI (Jones et al., 2021). Finally, GLEON, the Global Lake Ecological Observatory Network, presents itself as a “grassroots” network science initiative (Weathers et al. 2013). The flat and relatively fluid structure of GLEON is very different from the top-down institutional approach of the eLTER RI but they may still have important lessons for us. The GLEON culture is extremely successful at generating high impact, policy relevant science and nurturing early career researchers. A close study of how they do this and how the GLEON approach could be incorporated into the eLTER RI would contribute to the strategic goal to “invest in the next generation of European scientists and strengthen the diversity of our research community”.

4.3.4 RI Level of maturity

In addition to the spatial scales discussed above, research networks can be characterized by, e.g., their start date, primary purpose and current commitment to open science (Table 1 and Section 4.2.2). First generation infrastructures include “legacy” national networks and infrastructures that have been monitoring for decades or more and do not readily fit into an RI concept, e.g., initiatives such as long-term forest monitoring, soil surveys and agricultural experimental stations. There are some clear benefits to co-location with these sites in first generation RIs for giving some long-term temporal context to measurements made using eLTER standardized observations. For example, national forest inventories will extend the temporal perspective of vegetation measurements (Laudon et al. 2021) and agricultural experimental stations, such as the Ultuna long term soil organic matter experiment maintained by SLU (Kätterer et al. 2011), can give a long-term historical perspective on soil carbon dynamics.

⁷ <https://envri.eu/research-infrastructures/#1681825416408-f514dbe4-598b>

The ICPs are a good example of second generation infrastructures. Like eLTER, they are site based and collect standardized observations. Because the ICPs were originally established to provide data to support government decision making, they are not as advanced as eLTER in their commitment to open data but this is changing, in part due to interactions between people involved in both infrastructures.

Third generation RIs such as NEON and ICOS probably have the most similar organizational structure and vision to the eLTER RI. These RIs are characterized by a top-down centralized approach that prioritizes high quality standardized observations and state of the art IT infrastructure.

4.4 Collaboration and Co-location

Collaboration is at the heart of the eLTER vision and should remain a high priority in the further development of the RI. Co-location is one important dimension of collaboration. Co-location should focus on both physical and virtual aspects. The presence of multiple RIs and networks co-located at a single site will increase the scientific value both of the site and the participating networks. Virtual collaboration based on mutual learning and knowledge transfer is also extremely important. More mature RIs such as ICOS and NEON can offer guidance for best practices while eLTER can be an important agent for disseminating best practices such as the Standardized Observing protocols and IM/IT solutions such as DEIMS-SDR.

5 Virtual Co-location

The case for physical co-location, where multiple RIs make observations at the same sites is well accepted by funders and the scientific community. While physical co-location is a necessary part of the eLTER commitment to collaboration, it is not sufficient. Virtual co-location is also necessary. Defining physical co-location is straightforward: two or more networks or RIs make measurements at a single observing site. The concept of virtual co-location needs further explanation. The vision for virtual co-location presented in this deliverable is based on a search engine or e-commerce metaphor. A search engine (e.g., Google Scholar) compiles machine readable information from across the internet and presents it in a standardized manner. Effectively, a search engine for scientific publications is like a virtual library. It presents a catalogue of potentially relevant documents based on user-specified search criteria. An e-commerce platform (e.g., Amazon) works in the same way as it supports searches across multiple vendors in a consistent manner. It is important to note that there is a difference between machine discoverability and quality of the discovered items. Documents identified using scientific search engines must still be reviewed for quality. The same is true in this approach presented here. The goal of virtual co-location is solely to make datasets machine discoverable. Other issues, e.g., compliance to FAIR principles, are outside the scope of this document.

The workflow for virtual co-location presented in this chapter are the result of informal collaborations between staff in eLTER and ICOS. The workflows presented here can complement and augment the IT infrastructure that is planned and implemented within Work Packages 10 and 11 of the eLTER PLUS project. Here, we draw from our experiences in the Science Cases of Work Package 9 to provide some guidance for future IM/IT services that could be developed in the RI roadmap.

5.1 Conceptual Approach

Having results from multiple locations across the internet displayed in a single portal says nothing about the quality of the results. A Google Scholar search can identify candidate publications, but human intervention (i.e., reading them and reflecting on what is written) is still needed to assess their

fitness for purpose. Similarly, an Amazon search may collate offerings from multiple vendors but a “buyer beware” attitude is needed to identify regret-free purchases.

The benefits of freely accessible search engines for scientific literature are hard to overstate. The process of discovering potentially relevant literature used to work very differently in the past than it does today. It was not so long ago that we accessed scientific literature in a much less efficient manner than we do today. Discovery came either with the arrival of the latest issues of a few selected journals, or for those lucky enough to have the necessary credentials or affiliation, time spent in a university library. Acquiring copies of interesting papers was time consuming and labour intensive. A typical workflow consisted of a scientist reading an article in a paper journal and then asking a secretary to type a letter to the corresponding author asking for a reprint. The secretary would then post the physical letter, which would then be received by another secretary, who would post a reprint back to the first secretary. This process was labour intensive and slow. The availability of early proprietary search engines for scientific literature (e.g., Web of Science) was a step forward but they retained the exclusivity of university libraries. To use these early search engines, it was necessary to be behind a pay wall.

Today, anyone can go to Google Scholar, hunt around for a while and ideally find and download open access pdf copies of interesting articles. There are a number of points to raise about this approach. First, the process requires human intervention. Second, publishers have to make metadata machine discoverable for documents to be indexed by the search engine. Third, the process relies on proprietary but widely available technology and standards (the most obvious example is the use of the Adobe Portable Document Format, but there are others). The Adobe pdf format is publicly accessible but proprietary. The existence and widespread use of standard formats facilitates information exchange. The proposal presented here relies on a publicly accessible metadata format⁸ that facilitates machine discovery. Fourth, someone has to pay the open access charges. Finally, the process is search engine agnostic. It does not rely on Google Scholar, other search engines will deliver similar results.

Evaluating scientific documents found online is not a fully automated process. Someone still has to read at least some of the article to see if it is what they are looking for but it does highlight the benefits of machine searchable metadata for discovering and obtaining scientific documents. “Machine discoverable” is not the same as “credible” or “fit for purpose”. A buyer beware attitude and a healthy dose of scepticism are needed when evaluating Google Scholar searches, and will be needed with virtual co-location.

As well as developing a system for searching machine readable data about the scientific literature, Google have also developed Google Dataset Search (GDS), a system for searching publicly accessible datasets (Brickley et al. 2018). Currently, the system indexes about 25 million individual datasets, including a number of those collected by eLTER.

There are at least two workflows currently in use within the eLTER PLUS project for making metadata about datasets machine discoverable. One is implemented centrally in B2Find, the other is a distributed workflow developed by the ICOS Carbon Portal. Both workflows generate machine discoverable data that can be collated by search tools including GDS.

The DEIMS->B2Share->B2Find workflow is a good first step as it currently makes some of the eLTER data sets machine discoverable. While this is encouraging, there are some shortcomings to the workflow in its current implementation. Preliminary investigations suggest that B2Find does not appear to make all datasets stored in B2Share and catalogued in DEIMS machine discoverable using

⁸<https://schema.org/>

GDS. This finding may highlight shortcomings in the investigation, shortcomings in the workflow or a conscious decision not to make all DEIMS datasets stored in B2Share machine discoverable. The second and potentially more serious reservation is that the workflow requires support from the eLTER IM/IT team. While the eLTER project is fortunate to have a number of dedicated and highly competent people, they all appear to be seriously overcommitted. Any workflow that does not make additional demands on them is very attractive.

The workflow developed by the ICOS Carbon Portal to make datasets machine discoverable is attractive for a number of reasons. From the perspective of this task, it is noteworthy that a national level ERNI (SITES) has implemented a protocol originally developed ICOS. This example of a successful technology transfer between RIs is not primarily the result of co-location but it does highlight the benefits of close communication between RIs. Another key benefit is that the workflow can be rolled out at the individual site level and needs minimal input from the central eLTER IT/IM team. One of the biggest benefit of the proposed workflow is that it exists today. It is based on a mature, low effort technology that is supported by tools that are in use today

5.2 Lessons from ICOS

There are a number of lessons eLTER can learn from ICOS. As noted by Jaana Bäck in her 2022 ICOS Science Conference Presentation, “ICOS is the big sister and eLTER wants to be like her but is a bit conflicted due to a combination of admiration and jealousy”. In multiple attempts to build stronger ties between ICOS and eLTER, there has been agreement on both sides that ICOS is a more mature RI, eLTER can learn from ICOS and that further progress towards RI status would benefit from critical reflection on this situation.

ICOS has been successful for a number of reasons, not the least of which is its ability to collect and publicize standardized, quality controlled data. However, this is not the primary reason for the success of the RI. One of the main reasons ICOS is a success is because it has been able to make good use of new technologies. Prior to the establishment of the ICOS RI, atmospheric gas flux measurements were being made, but they were difficult and expensive. The key point that made ICOS successful was the availability of (relatively) inexpensive and easy to use flux measurement technology that made it possible for ICOS to develop their network of standardized observations. Without wanting to downplay the success of ICOS, what they have managed to do is a lot less complicated than what we are trying to do with standard observations. They measure one set of processes (gas fluxes) and they do it really well.

ICOS is only one of many successful RIs that can offer inspiration and guidance for best practices. We are trying to measure a broad suite of environmental and social phenomena. We can learn more from the US NEON infrastructure as they have wrestled with the challenges of developing standard observation protocols for a broad range of subject areas including, e.g., biodiversity (Li et al. 2022) and soil chemistry (Weintraub-Lee et al. 2023).

5.3 Example Workflow

Google Dataset Search (GDS) is currently the major portal for retrieving machine readable metadata about publicly accessible datasets. The GDS interface is similar to Google Scholar and other Google search products. The following web address lists all the datasets found by GDS that are managed by ICOS, SITES and the Swedish Svartberget Research Station:

<https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/search?src=0&query=Svartberget&docid=L2cvMTFueDd0eTFjMA%3D%3D&filters=WyJbXCJvcmdhbmI6YXRpb25fbWlkXCIsW1wiL2cvMTF0MG0z>

a3E1MVwiLFwiL2cvMTF0MG0zOXNueFwiLFwiL2cvMTF0MG0zOWpfNlwiXV0iXQ%3D%3D&property=b3JnYW5pemF0aW9uX21pZA%3D%3D

Having machine discoverable data would have reduced the effort needed to complete Task 8.3⁹. Virtual co-location through machine discoverable datasets would have greatly streamlined the attempts to model ecosystem response to drought at Svartberget using eLTER and ICOS data. The dataflow was more labour intensive than it would have been if datasets were machine discoverable. The ICOS data were retrieved and sent to another group for use in modelling. Internet searches were then conducted to identify additional data needed to complete the task. Now that the ICOS and SITES datasets have machine discoverable metadata, this process could have been considerably streamlined through virtual co-location.

To summarize, “streamlined” supports “scalable”. The SITES workflows adopted from ICOS could be rolled out across the eLTER network through video-based training or peer to peer actions. Empowering individual sites within the network to make their data machine discoverable would be a good example of the value added for both sites and national funders by participation in the eLTER RI.

Supporting and promoting the workflows for virtual co-location through making datasets machine discoverable offers the potential for significant reward with limited additional effort. We propose that eLTER follow the SITES model and strongly promote adding searchable structured data to the landing page of eLTER data sets. This could be a relatively straight forward process as the structured data format is based on public and open standards¹⁰.

Adding machine searchable metadata to the landing page for a dataset is a first step towards virtual co-location, but it is certainly not the last. Machine searchable metadata will not make a dataset FAIR (Wilkinson et al. 2016), it will not make any promises as to the quality of the data, nor will it ensure that the data are used in an appropriate manner. However, widespread use of machine searchable metadata could give the scientific community similar benefits to those currently obtained from using journal search engines, e.g., Google Scholar.

The approach proposed here to achieve virtual co-location by making datasets machine discoverable does not require GDS. Currently, GDS is the largest player for data set searches but in the same way as there are other search engines (e.g., Bing), there are other search systems that can read the structured metadata. So, a recommendation for the GDS as a data discovery tool is not an endorsement for any particular product, and the viability of this proposal does not depend on any single software vendor. The proposal is based exclusively on open standards and has a relatively low bar for entry that could make it interesting to individual sites or national consortia.

To promote virtual co-location, the eLTER RI should be promoting new workflows that allow for the creation and consumption of machine readable metadata. The eLTER PLUS project is making some important steps in this direction with the development of centralized IM/IT systems but these do not address the need for virtual co-location presented here.

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⁹ Task 8.3 –Water use efficiency (WUE) of ecosystems and resilience to drought

¹⁰ <https://schema.org/>

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7 References

Arora, B., Kuppel, S., Wellen, C., Oswald, C., Groh, J., Payandi-Rolland, D., Stegen, J. and Coffinet, S., 2023. Building Cross-Site and Cross-Network collaborations in critical zone science. *Journal of Hydrology*, p.129248.

Brümmer, C., Marx, O., Kutsch, W.L., Ammann, C., Wolff, V., Flechard, C.R. and Freibauer, A., 2013. Fluxes of total reactive atmospheric nitrogen (Sigma Nr) using eddy covariance above arable land. *Tellus B: Chemical and Physical Meteorology*, 65(1), p.19770.

Cabon, A., Kannenberg, S.A., Arain, A., Babst, F., Baldocchi, D., Belmecheri, S., Delpierre, N., Guerrieri, R., Maxwell, J.T., McKenzie, S. and Meinzer, F.C., 2022. Cross-biome synthesis of source versus sink limits to tree growth. *Science*, 376(6594), pp.758-761.

Ceccherini, G., Duveiller, G., Grassi, G., Lemoine, G., Avitabile, V., Pilli, R. and Cescatti, A., 2020. Abrupt increase in harvested forest area over Europe after 2015. *Nature*, 583(7814), pp.72-77.

Chi, J., Nilsson, M.B., Kljun, N., Wallerman, J., Fransson, J.E., Laudon, H., Lundmark, T. and Peichl, M., 2019. The carbon balance of a managed boreal landscape measured from a tall tower in northern Sweden. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 274, pp.29-41.

Cleverly, J., Eamus, D., Edwards, W., Grant, M., Grundy, M.J., Held, A., Karan, M., Lowe, A.J., Prober, S.M., Sparrow, B. and Morris, B., 2019. TERN, Australia's land observatory: addressing the global challenge of forecasting ecosystem responses to climate variability and change. *Environmental Research Letters*, 14(9), p.095004.

Dirnböck, T., Pröll, G., Austnes, K., Beloica, J., Beudert, B., Canullo, R., De Marco, A., Fornasier, M.F., Futter, M., Goergen, K. and Grandin, U., 2018. Currently legislated decreases in nitrogen deposition will yield only limited plant species recovery in European forests. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(12), p.125010.

Dirnböck, T., Haase, P., Mirtl, M., Pauw, J., Templer, P.H., 2019. Contemporary International Long-Term Ecological Research (ILTER)—from biogeosciences to socio-ecology and biodiversity research. *Regional Environmental Change* 19(2), 309-311.

European Commission. 2019. The European Green Deal. COM(2019) 640 final. European Commission, Brussels, 24pp.

Ezzati, G., Kyllmar, K. and Barron, J., 2023. Long-term water quality monitoring in agricultural catchments in Sweden: Impact of climatic drivers on diffuse nutrient loads. *Science of the Total Environment*, 864, p.160978.

Ferrara, R.M., Loubet, B., Di Tommasi, P., Bertolini, T., Magliulo, V., Cellier, P., Eugster, W. and Rana, G., 2012. Eddy covariance measurement of ammonia fluxes: Comparison of high frequency correction methodologies. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 158, pp.30-42.

Ferretti, M., 2021. New appetite for the monitoring of European forests. *Annals of Forest Science*, 78, pp.1-4.

Futter, M.N., Högbom, L., Valinia, S., Sponseller, R.A. and Laudon, H., 2016. Conceptualizing and communicating management effects on forest water quality. *Ambio*, 45(2), pp.188-202.

Futter, M., Ashraful Alam, S., Baatz, R., Bäck, J., Diaz-Pines, E., Dick, J., Forsius, M., Gaube, V., Jones, M., Nikolaidis, N. and Poppe, C., 2021, April. Amplifying Signals and avoiding surprises: Potential synergies between ICOS and eLTER at the Water-Climates-Greenhouse Gas nexus. In EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts (pp. EGU21-9567).

Futter, M.N., Dirnböck, T., Forsius, M., Bäck, J.K., Cools, N., Diaz-Pines, E., Dick, J., Gaube, V., Gillespie, L.M., Högbom, L. and Laudon, H., 2023. Leveraging research infrastructure co-location to evaluate constraints on terrestrial carbon cycling in northern European forests. *Ambio*, 52(11), pp.1819-1831.

Geranmayeh P., K.M. Johannesson, B. Ulén & K.S. Tonderski. 2018. Particle deposition, resuspension and phosphorus accumulation in small constructed wetlands. *Ambio* 47: 134-145.

Grennfelt, P., Engleryd, A., Forsius, M., Hov, Ø., Rodhe, H. and Cowling, E. 2020. Acid rain and air pollution— 50 years of progress in environmental science and policy. *Ambio* 49: 849–864. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-019-01244-4>.

Guintoli, J., Searle, S., Jonsson, R., Agostini, A., Robert, N., Amaducci, S., Marelli, L. and Camia, A., 2020. Carbon accounting of bioenergy and forest management nexus. A reality-check of modeling assumptions and expectations. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 134, p.110368.

Haase, P., Bowler, D.E., Baker, N.J., Bonada, N., Domisch, S., Garcia Marquez, J.R., Heino, J., Hering, D., Jähnig, S.C., Schmidt-Kloiber, A. and Stubbington, R., 2023. The recovery of European freshwater biodiversity has come to a halt. *Nature*, 620(7974), pp.582-588.

Hari, P., Nikinmaa, E., Pohja, T., Siivola, E., Bäck, J., Vesala, T. and Kulmala, M., 2013. Station for measuring ecosystem-atmosphere relations: SMEAR. *Physical and physiological forest ecology*, pp.471-487.

Heidorn, P.B., 2008. Shedding light on the dark data in the long tail of science. *Library trends*, 57(2), pp.280-299.

Heiskanen, J., Brümmer, C., Buchmann, N., Calfapietra, C., Chen, H., Gielen, B., Gkritzalis, T., Hammer, S., Hartman, S., Herbst, M. and Janssens, I.A., 2022. The integrated carbon observation system in Europe. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 103(3), pp.E855-E872.

Huber, R., D'Onofrio, C., Devaraju, A., Klump, J., Loescher, H.W., Kindermann, S., Guru, S., Grant, M., Morris, B., Wyborn, L. and Evans, B., 2021. Integrating data and analysis technologies within leading environmental research infrastructures: Challenges and approaches. *Ecological Informatics*, 61, p.101245.

Högbom, L., Abbas, D., Armolaitis, K., Baders, E., Futter, M., Jansons, A., Jögiste, K., Lazdins, A., Lukminè, D., Mustonen, M. and Øistad, K., 2021. Trilemma of Nordic–Baltic Forestry—How to Implement UN Sustainable Development Goals. *Sustainability*, 13(10), p.5643.

Jiménez, S.M., Saunders, M., Denge, S., Kolari, P., Moureaux, C., Montagnani, L., Ceschia, E., Altimir, N., López-Ballesteros, A., Acosta, M. and Klumpp, K., 2018. Importance of reporting ancillary site

characteristics, and management and disturbance information at ICOS stations. *International Agrophysics*, 32(4), pp.457-469.

Jones, J.A., Groffman, P.M., Blair, J., Davis, F.W., Dugan, H., Euskirchen, E.E., Frey, S.D., Harms, T.K., Hinckley, E., Kosmala, M. and Loberg, S., 2021. Synergies among environmental science research and monitoring networks: a research agenda. *Earth's Future*, 9(3), p.e2020EF001631.

Keller, M., Schimel, D. and Hoffman, F.M., 2008. A Continental Strategy for the National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON). *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 6(5): 282-284.

Kvaeven, B., Ulstein, M.J., Skjelkvåle, B.L., Raddum, G.G. and Hovind, H., 2001. ICP Waters—an international programme for surface water monitoring. *Water, air, and soil pollution*, 130, pp.775-780.

Kätterer, T., Bolinder, M.A., Andrén, O., Kirchmann, H. and Menichetti, L., 2011. Roots contribute more to refractory soil organic matter than above-ground crop residues, as revealed by a long-term field experiment. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 141(1-2), pp.184-192.

Laudon, H., Hasselquist, E.M., Peichl, M., Lindgren, K., Sponseller, R., Lidman, F., Kuglerova, L., Hasselquist, N.J., Bishop, K., Nilsson, M.B. and Ågren, A.M., 2021. Northern landscapes in transition: Evidence, approach and ways forward using the Krycklan Catchment Study. *Hydrological Processes*, 35(4), p.e14170.

Li, D., Record, S., Sokol, E.R., Bitters, M.E., Chen, M.Y., Chung, Y.A., Helmus, M.R., Jaimes, R., Jansen, L., Jarzyna, M.A. and Just, M.G., 2022. Standardized NEON organismal data for biodiversity research. *Ecosphere*, 13(7), p.e4141.

Lilli, M.A., Efstathiou, D., Moraetis, D., Schuite, J., Nerantzaki, S.D. and Nikolaidis, N.P., 2020. A multi-disciplinary approach to understand hydrologic and geochemical processes at koiliaris critical zone observatory. *Water*, 12(9), p.2474.

McRoberts, R.E., Tomppo, E.O. and Næsset, E., 2010. Advances and emerging issues in national forest inventories. *Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research*, 25(4), pp.368-381.

Migliavacca, M., Musavi, T., Mahecha, M.D., Nelson, J.A., Knauer, J., Baldocchi, D.D., Perez-Priego, O., Christiansen, R., Peters, J., Anderson, K. and Bahn, M., 2021. The three major axes of terrestrial ecosystem function. *Nature*, 598(7881), pp.468-472.

Mirtl, M., Kuhn, I., Montheith, D., Bäck, J., Orenstein, D., Provenzale, A., Zacharias, S., Haase, P. and Shachak, M., 2021, April. Whole System Approach for in-situ research on Life Supporting Systems in the Anthropocene (WAILS). In *EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts* (pp. EGU21-16425).

Mirtl, M., Borer, E.T., Djukic, I., Forsius, M., Haubold, H., Hugo, W., Jourdan, J., Lindenmayer, D., McDowell, W.H., Muraoka, H. and Orenstein, D.E., 2018. Genesis, goals and achievements of long-term ecological research at the global scale: a critical review of ILTER and future directions. *Science of the total Environment*, 626, pp.1439-1462.

Nagy, R.C., Balch, J.K., Bissell, E.K., Cattau, M.E., Glenn, N.F., Halpern, B.S., Ilangakoon, N., Johnson, B., Joseph, M.B., Marconi, S. and O’Riordan, C., 2021. Harnessing the NEON data revolution to advance open environmental science with a diverse and data-capable community. *Ecosphere*, 12(12), p.e03833.

Napa, Ü., Kabral, N., Liiv, S., Asi, E., Timmusk, T. and Frey, J., 2015. Current and historical patterns of heavy metals pollution in Estonia as reflected in natural media of different ages: ICP Vegetation, ICP Forests and ICP Integrated Monitoring data. *Ecological Indicators*, 52, pp.31-39.

Noe, S.M., Niinemets, Ü., Krasnova, A., Krasnov, D., Motallebi, A., Kängsepp, V., Jõgiste, K., Hörrak, U., Komsaare, K., Mirme, S. and Vana, M., 2015. SMEAR Estonia: Perspectives of a large-scale forest ecosystem–atmosphere research infrastructure. *Forestry studies*, 63(1), pp.56-84.

Penuelas, J., Fernández-Martínez, M., Vallicrosa, H., Maspons, J., Zuccarini, P., Carnicer, J., Sanders, T.G., Krüger, I., Obersteiner, M., Janssens, I.A. and Ciais, P., 2020. Increasing atmospheric CO₂ concentrations correlate with declining nutritional status of European forests. *Communications biology*, 3(1), pp.1-11.

Poikane, S., Birk, S., Böhmer, J., Carvalho, L., de Hoyos, C., Gassner, H., Hellsten, S., Kelly, M., Solheim, A.L., Olin, M. and Pall, K., 2015. A hitchhiker's guide to European lake ecological assessment and intercalibration. *Ecological indicators*, 52, pp.533-544.

Pongratz, J., Schwingshackl, C., Bultan, S., Obermeier, W., Havermann, F. and Guo, S., 2021. Land use effects on climate: current state, recent Progress, and emerging topics. *Current Climate Change Reports*, pp.1-22.

Rennie, S., K. Goergen, C. Wohner, S. Apweiler, J. Peterseil, and J. Watkins. 2021. A climate service for ecologists: sharing pre-processed EURO-CORDEX regional climate scenario data using the eLTER Information System. *Earth System Science Data* 13 (2): 631–644.

Vuorenmaa, J., Augustaitis, A., Beudert, B., Clarke, N., de Wit, H.A., Dirnböck, T., Frey, J., Forsius, M., Indrikson, I., Kleemola, S. and Kobler, J., 2017. Long-term sulphate and inorganic nitrogen mass balance budgets in European ICP Integrated Monitoring catchments (1990–2012). *Ecological Indicators*, 76, pp.15-29.

Weathers, K., Hanson, P.C., Arzberger, P., Brenttrup, J., Brookes, J.D., Carey, C.C., Gaiser, E., Hamilton, D.P., Hong, G.S., Ibelings, B.W. and Istvánovics, V., 2013. The Global Lake Ecological Observatory Network (GLEON): the evolution of grassroots network science.

Weintraub-Leff, S.R., Hall, S.J., Craig, M.E., Sihi, D., Wang, Z. and Hart, S.C., 2023. Standardized data to improve understanding and modeling of soil nitrogen at continental scale. *Earth's Future*, 11(5), p.e2022EF003224.

Wettestad, J., 1997. Acid lessons? LRTAP implementation and effectiveness. *Global Environmental Change*, 7(3), pp.235-249.

Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.W., da Silva Santos, L.B., Bourne, P.E. and Bouwman, J., 2016. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*, 3(1), pp.1-9.

Wohner, C., Peterseil, J., Poursanidis, D., Kliment, T., Wilson, M., Mirtl, M. and Chrysoulakis, N., 2019. DEIMS-SDR—A web portal to document research sites and their associated data. *Ecological Informatics*, 51, pp.15-24.

Wohner, C., Peterseil, J., Genazzio, M.A., Guru, S., Hugo, W. and Klug, H., 2020. Towards interoperable research site documentation—Recommendations for information models and data provision. *Ecological Informatics*, 60, p.101158.

Wohner, C., Ohnemus, T., Zacharias, S., Mollenhauer, H., Ellis, E.C., Klug, H., Shibata, H. and Mirtl, M., 2021. Assessing the biogeographical and socio-ecological representativeness of the ILTER site network. *Ecological Indicators*, 127, p.107785.

Wohner, C., Peterseil, J. and Klug, H., 2022. Designing and implementing a data model for describing environmental monitoring and research sites. *Ecological Informatics*, 70, p.101708.

Xu, L., Saatchi, S.S., Yang, Y., Yu, Y., Pongratz, J., Bloom, A.A., Bowman, K., Worden, J., Liu, J., Yin, Y. and Domke, G., 2021. Changes in global terrestrial live biomass over the 21st century. *Science Advances*, 7(27), p.eabe9829.

Zacharias, S., Bogena, H., Samaniego, L., Mauder, M., Fuß, R., Pütz, T., Frenzel, M., Schwank, M., Baessler, C., Butterbach-Bahl, K. and Bens, O., 2011. A network of terrestrial environmental observatories in Germany. *Vadose Zone Journal*, 10(3), pp.955-973.

8 Glossary

Abbreviation	Expansion
ACTRIS	The Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure
AnaEE	Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems
CLRTAP	Convention on Long Range Transport of Air Pollution
CZO	Critical Zone Observatory
DANUBIUS	International Centre for Advanced Studies on River-Sea Systems
DEIMS	Dynamic Ecological Information Management System
EGU	European Geosciences Union
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research
eLTSER	Long Term Socio Ecological Research
EMEP	European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme
ENVRI	EU Cluster for Environmental Research Infrastructures
ERNIs	Environmental Research Networks and Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDS	Google Dataset Search
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GLEON	Global Lake Ecological Observatory Network
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
ICP IM	International Cooperative Programme on Integrated Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Ecosystems
ILTER	International Long Term Ecological Research
INTERACT	International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic
LLO	Long-term Legacy Observation
LTER	Long Term Ecological Research
NEON	US National Ecological Observatory Network
NFI	National Forest Inventory
PRI	Policy Relevant Indicator
RI	Research Infrastructure
SITES	The Swedish Infrastructure for Ecosystem Science
SMEAR	Station for Measuring Ecosystem-Atmosphere Exchange
SO	Standard Observation
TERENO	Terrestrial Environmental Observatories
TERN	Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
VRP	Verifiable Regional Prediction
WGE	Working Group on Effects